

Evaluating unit test code in python generated by GitHub Copilot

Dear participant,

This form is part of an academic research project that aims to investigate the quality of test code generated by Large Language Models (LLMs), with a specific focus on GitHub Copilot for Python. Your feedback is extremely important for the advancement of this study and will contribute to understanding the effectiveness and reliability of automated tests produced by language models.

Please take a few minutes to evaluate the test cases presented in this form. There will be 6 evaluations and the average response time will vary from 10 to 15 minutes. Your comments will be used to analyze the clarity, correctness and suitability of the tests generated by LLM. In addition, your evaluation will help us to identify possible patterns of errors or inadequacies in the tests produced by the model.

Your answers will be treated confidentially and used for academic research purposes only. There are no right or wrong answers; we only ask for your honest and objective opinion.

We sincerely thank you for your participation and collaboration in this study.

* Indica uma pergunta obrigatória

1. E-mail *

2. Informed Consent Form

*

We would like to invite you to participate as a volunteer to answer the form EVALUATING UNIT TEST CODES IN PYTHON GENERATED BY GITHUB COPILOT. The reason we are carrying out this questionnaire is to assess the quality of the test code generated by LLMs.

To do this, you will be asked to review and evaluate submitted test cases, providing feedback on their quality and suitability.

****Please note**

All information provided will be confidential and used for academic research purposes only.

Furthermore, this survey will at no time seek to evaluate your answers as right or wrong.

****Contact**

If you have any questions about the objectives of this questionnaire, please contact us at the following e-mail address: -

Marcar apenas uma oval.

I declare that I agree to participate in the research and authorize the disclosure of the information provided by me in congresses and/or scientific publications as long as no data can identify me.

I do not wish to take part in this survey.

Personal Information

In this section, you will evaluate your professional profile and your knowledge of the areas of interest in this survey.

3. How long have you been working in Software Engineering? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- I've never worked in Software Engineering
- Less than 1 year
- Between 1 and 2 years
- Between 2 and 5 years
- Between 5 and 7 years
- More than 7 years

4. Which of the options below best describes your current position?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Software Developer
- Test or quality analyst/engineer (QA)
- Requirements analyst/engineer
- Project Analyst/Manager
- Tech Lead
- Outro: _____

5. What is your academic background?

Marcar apenas uma oval.

- Graduated / Graduate
- Master's student / Master
- Doctoral student / Doctor

6. Assess your level of knowledge in the following areas: *

Marcar apenas uma oval por linha.

	I have no knowledge	Basic knowledge	Intermediate knowledge	Advanced knowledge	Specialized knowledge
Python	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Unit Testing	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Test Smells	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7. Have you ever used a Generative AI (Copilot, ChatGPT) or other tool to automatically generate test code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

8. Have you ever participated in projects that involved analyzing and evaluating the quality of test code? *

Marcar apenas uma oval.

Yes

No

How this survey will work

In the following sections, you will be shown some test codes and you will have to assess the presence of some specific characteristics.

Instructions for answers:

I - All the following codes are test functions/methods written in python with the pytest and unittest libraries. Each test case is named CT01, CT02 ... CTn.

II - For each test, a link to the corresponding production code is attached in case you need to look it up;

III - For each test, there is a list of characteristics that you should mark if you identify their presence in the code. You can mark one or more characteristics that you have detected.

IV - If you identify another characteristic in the codes that is not listed, describe it in the Other option.

V - If you haven't identified any of the characteristics listed and you think the code is correct according to your perception, point out in the Other option that no problems were identified in the tests.

VI - At the end of each evaluation, you can suggest improvements for each test that has been evaluated. If you wish to suggest improvements, it is recommended that you highlight which test case (CT01, CT02 ... CTn) your improvement refers to. The suggestion is optional.

VII - This is an empirical survey, i.e. you will have to use your experience to evaluate the tests, there is no categorization of right or wrong answers

Click Next to start the evaluation

Evaluation 1/6

9. The image below shows two test cases that test methods of a class called Notifiable: *

CT01 - test_notifiable_add_notifications()

CT02 - test_notifiable_get_notifications()

Analyze them and mark which characteristics you can observe in these tests.

Production code available [HERE](#)

```

17  def test_notifiable_add_notifications():
18      notifiable = Notifiable()
19      notifications = [Notification('key1', 'message1'), Notification('key2', 'message2')]
20      notifiable.add_notifications(notifications)
21      assert not notifiable.is_valid
22      assert len(notifiable.notifications) == 2
23      assert notifiable.notifications == notifications
24
25  def test_notifiable_get_notifications():
26      notifiable = Notifiable()
27      notifications = [Notification('key1', 'message1'), Notification('key2', 'message2')]
28      notifiable.add_notifications(notifications)
29      assert notifiable.get_notifications() == notifications

```

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- There are several asserts without any explanation or message
- There are control statements (if, for, while...) in at least one test
- There are numeric literal values (-1, 2, 56...) in at least one test
- There are duplicate asserts in the same test
- There is at least one test that has no asserts
- The tests invoke various functions/methods/classes from the production code
- Outro: _____

10. If you would like to suggest any improvements to the codes you have evaluated, please describe them below:

Evaluation 2/6

11. The image below shows three test cases that test methods of a class called LottieProp:

CT03 - test_basic_to_dict_with_list_of_lists_v()

CT04 - test_clone_value_with_invalid_value()

CT05 - test_clone_value_with_mixed_list_value()

Analyze them and mark which characteristics you can observe in these tests

Full test code available [HERE](#)

Production code available [HERE](#)

```
38     def test_basic_to_dict_with_list_of_lists_v():
39         prop = LottieProp("test", int, 0)
40         result = prop._basic_to_dict([[1, 2], [3, 4]])
41         assert result == [[1, 2], [3, 4]]
42
43     def test_clone_value_with_invalid_value():
44         prop = LottieProp("test", int, 0)
45         with pytest.raises(Exception):
46             prop.clone_value({})
47
48     def test_clone_value_with_mixed_list_value():
49         prop = LottieProp("test", int, 0)
50         result = prop.clone_value([1, "foo", True])
51         assert result == [1, "foo", True]
```

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- There are several asserts without any explanation or message
- There are control statements (if, for, while...) in at least one test
- There are numeric literal values (-1, 2, 56...) in at least one test
- There are duplicate asserts in the same test
- There is at least one test that has no asserts
- The tests invoke various functions/methods/classes from the production code
- Outro: _____

12. If you would like to suggest any improvements to the codes you have evaluated, please describe them below:

Evaluation 3/6

13. The image below has two test cases that test methods of a class called KeyFrame: *

CTo6 - test_keyframe_bezier_from_keyframe()

CTo7 - test_animatable_mixin_clear_animation()

Analyze them and mark which characteristics you can observe in these tests

Full test code available [HERE](#)

Production code available [HERE](#)

```
4  ✓ def test_keyframe_bezier_from_keyframe():
5      keyframe = Keyframe()
6      keyframe.out_value = 1
7      keyframe.in_value = 2
8      obj = KeyframeBezier.from_keyframe(keyframe)
9      assert obj.h1 == 1
10     assert obj.h2 == 2
11
12
13  ✓ def test_animatable_mixin_clear_animation():
14     obj = AnimatableMixin()
15     obj.clear_animation(123)
16     assert obj.value == 123
17     assert obj.animated == False
18     assert obj.keyframes == None
```

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- There are several asserts without any explanation or message
- There are control statements (if, for, while...) in at least one test
- There are numeric literal values (-1, 2, 56...) in at least one test
- There are duplicate asserts in the same test
- There is at least one test that has no asserts
- The tests invoke various functions/methods/classes from the production code
- Outro: _____

14. If you would like to suggest any improvements to the codes you have evaluated, please describe them below:

Evaluation 4/6

15. The image below shows three test cases that test the behavior of the `CollectionsValidationContract` class: *

CT08 - `test_is_between_with_list_within_range()`

CT09 - `test_is_between_with_list_below_range()`

CT10 - `test_is_between_with_list_above_range()`

Analyze them and mark which characteristics you can observe in these tests

Production code available [HERE](#)

```

4     def test_is_between_with_list_within_range():
5         contract = CollectionsValidationContract()
6         contract.is_between([1, 2, 3], 1, 3, 'key', 'message')
7         assert contract.is_valid
8
9     def test_is_between_with_list_below_range():
10        contract = CollectionsValidationContract()
11        contract.is_between([1], 2, 3, 'key', 'message')
12        assert not contract.is_valid
13        assert len(contract.get_notifications()) == 1
14        assert contract.get_notifications()[0].message == 'message'
15
16    def test_is_between_with_list_above_range():
17        contract = CollectionsValidationContract()
18        contract.is_between([1, 2, 3, 4], 1, 3, 'key', 'message')
19        assert not contract.is_valid
20        assert len(contract.get_notifications()) == 1
21        assert contract.get_notifications()[0].message == 'message'

```

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- There are several asserts without any explanation or message
- There are control statements (if, for, while...) in at least one test
- There are numeric literal values (-1, 2, 56...) in at least one test
- There are duplicate asserts in the same test
- There is at least one test that has no asserts
- The tests invoke various functions/methods/classes from the production code
- Outro: _____

16. If you would like to suggest any improvements to the codes you have evaluated, please describe them below:

Evaluation 5/6

17. The image below shows two test cases inserted into a TestSifBuilder suite that test a class called ShapeLayer: *

CT11- test_non_empty(self)

CT12 - test_empty_layers(self)

Analyze them and mark which characteristics you can observe in these tests

Production code available [HERE](#)

```

7  class TestSifBuilder(TestCase):
8
9  def test_non_empty(self):
10     """Test if to_sif correctly converts a non-empty Animation."""
11     lot = objects.Animation()
12     lot.width = 123
13     lot.height = 456
14     lot.frame_rate = 69
15     lot.in_point = 3
16     lot.out_point = 7
17     lot.name = "test"
18
19     # Add a layer to the animation
20     layer = objects.layers.ShapeLayer()
21     lot.add_layer(layer)
22
23     sif = builder.to_sif(lot)
24     self.assertEqual(len(sif.layers), 1)
25
26
27 def test_empty_layers(self):
28     """Test if to_sif correctly converts an empty Animation with layers."""
29     lot = objects.Animation()
30     layer = objects.layers.ShapeLayer()
31     lot.add_layer(layer)
32
33     sif = builder.to_sif(lot)
34     self.assertEqual(len(sif.layers), len(lot.layers))

```

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- There are several asserts without any explanation or message
- There are control statements (if, for, while...) in at least one test
- There are numeric literal values (-1, 2, 56...) in at least one test
- There are duplicate asserts in the same test
- There is at least one test that has no asserts
- The tests invoke various functions/methods/classes from the production code

Outro: _____

18. If you would like to suggest any improvements to the codes you have evaluated, please describe them below:

Avaliação 6/6

19. The image below shows three test cases that test functions that manipulate the numbers in a cpf:

CT13 - test_generate()

CT14 - test__hashdigit()

CT15- test__checksum()

Analyze them and mark which characteristics you can observe in these tests

Production code available [HERE](#)

```
33     def test_generate():
34         for _ in range(100):
35             cpf = generate()
36             assert is_valid(cpf) == True
37
38     def test__hashdigit():
39         assert _hashdigit("52599927765", 11) == 5
40         assert _hashdigit("52599927765", 10) == 6
41
42     def test__checksum():
43         assert _checksum("335451269") == '51'
44         assert _checksum("382916331") == '26'
```

Marque todas que se aplicam.

- There are several asserts without any explanation or message
- There are control statements (if, for, while...) in at least one test
- There are numeric literal values (-1, 2, 56...) in at least one test
- There are duplicate asserts in the same test
- There is at least one test that has no asserts
- The tests invoke various functions/methods/classes from the production code

20. If you would like to suggest any improvements to the codes you have evaluated, please describe them below:

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